

Electron-Donor-Acceptor Complexes of Some Pyridines and Quinolines by NMR Spectroscopy

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The NMR method has been used to determine the association constants of some pyridines and quinolines with 1,3,5-trinitrobenzene in carbon-tetrachloride. Also, the determination of some thermodynamic parameters for the association of 2-methylindole with 1,3,5-trinitrobenzene is made.

MULLIKEN¹ suggested that charge-transfer complexes play an important role in biological systems. Some possible implications have been discussed in a book by Szent-Gyorgyi². Many workers have produced evidence which, it is claimed, supports this proposition. Various aspects of the problems involved have been reviewed.³

However, the pyridinium ion is of particular biological interest³. Therefore, we report here the association constants and thermodynamic parameters for some heterocyclic compounds of biological interest.

An electron-donor molecule (D) may interact with an electron-acceptor molecule (A) to form a 1:1 complex (AD) by a reversible process. If we assume that the activity coefficients for the various species are unity, the equilibrium constant may be defined:

$$K_c = (AD)/(A)(D)$$

However, most determinations of K_c have been made by measurements of the optical absorption of a series of solutions containing D and A in equilibrium with the complex. It has been suggested⁴ that these determinations may be in error due to the possible breakdown of Beer's law in such solution mixtures.

An alternative method of evaluation K_c may be made from NMR spectroscopy⁵. The difference between the position of the proton absorption in a suitable electron-acceptor molecule when uncomplexed, compared with the position of the same proton absorption when the acceptor molecule is in equilibrium with an electron-donor-acceptor complex, may be used to obtain an estimate of K_c . Thermodynamic parameters (ΔH and ΔS) for 2-methyl-indole is also determined. From the plot of $\log K_c$ against $1/T$ should yield a straight line if the complex is formed in the ratio 1:1.

Experimental

The method used for evaluating K_c from NMR spectra is similar to that of Foster^{3,5}, using the following equation:

$$\Delta/(D) + \Delta K = \Delta_0 K$$

The difference Δ of the chemical shift of the acceptor in the absence of donor and in the presence of donor at various concentrations of donor, where, $(D) \gg (A)$ is measured for a series of solutions of different (D) . The difference Δ_0 , is the chemical shift for the pure complex in the solvent. It can be shown that for a given system, a plot of $\Delta/(D)$ against Δ should be linear with gradient $-K_c$.

All NMR measurements have been made on solutions made up gravimetrically in (5 mm) diameter tubes using Varian A60A spectrometer. The probe is thermostated at 37°. All measurements have been made at this temperature except the case of 2-methylindole, where the measurements have been made at different temperatures. All line positions were measured relative to tetramethylsilane as an internal reference. The estimated accuracy of the line positions is ± 0.5 cycles/sec.

Results and Discussion

The results of this work are shown in Table 1. Under the equation above, the plots of $\Delta/[D]$ against Δ have shown good straight lines indicating that complex formation is in the ratio of 1:1. Mean Δ values are not the maximum obtainable values. This is because the position of the proton chemical shifts of the acceptor were lying between the positions of the chemical shifts of the donor in the spectra and therefore concentrations of the donor were so chosen and varied so that to keep the acceptor protons appear between the donors proton shifts. This behaviour have been noticed in the compounds VII, quinoline and γ -methylquinoline.

TABLE I.—ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS FOR SOME 1,3,5-TRINITROBENZENE-PYRIDINE AND QUINOLINE COMPLEXES AT 37° IN CCl₄, TOGETHER WITH THE CHEMICAL SHIFT OF THE ACCEPTOR PROTON IN THE PURE COMPLEX, RELATIVE TO THE CHEMICAL SHIFT OF THE SAME PROTON IN THE FREE ACCEPTOR (Δ_0) DETERMINED BY AN N.M.R. METHOD.

Donor	Present		Others ³	
	K_c /kg mol ⁻¹	Δ_0 Hz	K^*	Δ_0 Hz
I. pyridine	—	—	1.47	7
II. α -methylpyridine	0.95	18.6	0.96	18
III. β -methylpyridine	1.7	9.0	1.96	11
IV. γ -methylpyridine	2.02	11.0	2.41	10
V. quinoline	3.5	61.14	—	—
VI. γ -methylquinoline	4.4	75.77	—	—
VII. 2-(2-pyridyl)-quinoline	3.31	114.42	—	—
VIII. 2-(3-pyridyl)-quinoline	2.61	71.17	—	—
IX. 2-(4-pyridyl)-quinoline	2.13	75.27	—	—
X. 2-(2-thiophenyl)-quinoline	7.88	73.38	—	—

* These are Fosters *et al.* values measured at 33.5°, quoted from reference 3.

K_c values are found in compound order X > VII < VIII < IX, while in the case of picolines are in the order IV > III > 2II.

The results of compounds VII, VIII, IX and X are shown in the figure. Complex X which contains the sulphur atom has shown a more negative slope. It seems that X has a higher value of K_c than the rest. This is expected since sulphur is less electronegative than nitrogen atom and that thiophene molecule has an ionization energy much lower than

that of pyridine, making its π orbital electrons more available for interaction with the acceptor.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\Delta/[D]$ against Δ for the complexes of 1,3,5-trinitrobenzene with some of the compounds numbered as in the table.

Methyl substitution in quinoline has increased the degree of association. This effect is noted in the case of 3-methyl and 4-methyl pyridine, while 2-methyl pyridine has shown the reverse effect.

Temperature variation of K_c was studied by Foster⁶ at 33.5° only. K_c is found here to decrease with the increase in temperature. A linear relationship was obtained for the plot of $\log K_c$ against $1/T$ for the temperature range 16°–49°. The enthalpy of formation obtained is found to be $\Delta H = -2.38$ kcal mole⁻¹ and $\Delta S = -6.07$ e.u. However, the enthalpy of formation for the indole-chloranil complex³ is found to be -1.9 kcal mole⁻¹.

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References

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